

PROJECT - RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

SMART community-led transition for Europe's Rural Areas

PROJECT IDENTIFIER: 2024HE_101084160_SMART ERA

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Innovation, knowledge exchange & EIP-AGRI >

 ONGOING | 2024 - 2027

 Italy, Bulgaria, Other, Finland, Spain, Slovenia, East Herzegovina

Context

Depopulation, mostly characterized by emigration of young people, is occurring in rural areas all over Europe. This has brought to an ageing phenomenon, as well as the emergence of several structural problems such as fewer job opportunities, degradation of infrastructures and a decreasing offer of services of general interest. However, the revolution in digitalisation with an increase of remote and location-free work opportunities is offering the chance to redirect some rural migration flows back. Interventions are thus needed to take up this opportunity and build on trends such as multi-local living to promote new greener, smaller, sustainable and innovative growth models. It is there where SMART ERA intervenes.

Objectives

The project will foster resilience in rural areas, by upgrading and co-designing, co-developing and co-validating with local communities a set of smart solutions, integrated within Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs) able to tackle pressing socio-economic and environmental challenges and promote a community-led transition pathway that will empower rural people to act for change. SMART ERA's main ambitions are: a) building the first large-scale European-wide solution for systematic rural data screening and smartness analysis; b) using co-design

methods and techniques to involve residents and stakeholders in the design and validation of SIPs, as well as in the collection of old and creation of new data sources; c) proposing a unified Smartness/Digital Maturity assessment method; d) providing unique and timely evidence-based and performance-focused recommendations to upgrade the new local, national and European policy instruments and enhance their efficiency and efficacy in supporting smart villages across the EU; e) fostering cooperation among pilot regions, as well as among the four EU macro-regional strategies and improve their rural communities' ability to address socio-economic and environmental challenges

Activities

The project lasts 48 months and include 7 WPs. The activities for the development and consolidation of the solutions will start with research and co-design providing induction of common needs and evidence that can drive rural development: learnings from the past relevant EU projects and initiatives, integrated multi-scale data sources and emerging needs from rural communities are taken over to provide driving requirements for the development phase. The outcomes of the piloting and testing phases will be assessed in terms of long-term impacts: this is the basis for the development of a sustainability plan and maximisation of the project impact. In order to achieve the interplay, the project adopts a multidisciplinary four-step approach.

STEP 1 Inception: will leverage information on the framework in which the project will be executed to define an effective multidimensional methodology for the rural smartness assessment and the selection of the innovations to develop and integrate into the SIPs.

STEP 2 Development: will deliver the key outputs and components to be integrated into the SIPs. An Open Call will be launched for providing financial support to third parties (SMEs, tech providers) in the pilot regions to develop solutions for the SIPs.

STEP 3 Piloting: parallel validation activities within the pilot regions, in the context of which the different solutions and components will continue to evolve in order to track the requirements and needs of the involved rural communities. By the end of the phase, enhanced versions of the SIPs will be in place.

STEP 4 Transition: will capitalise on the results and lessons learned to foster knowledge exchange, deliver policy recommendations and the toolkit at the national and EU level and

spread out the tested solutions and methods in further rural areas. A second Open Call will be launched to find at least four follower rural regions willing to adopt the methodology and develop their own SIPs.

Project details

Main funding source

Horizon Europe (EU Research and Innovation Programme)

Type of Horizon project

Multi-actor project

Project acronym

SMART ERA

[CORDIS Fact sheet](#)

Project contribution to CAP specific objectives

- SO2. Increasing competitiveness: the role of productivity
- SO4. Agriculture and climate mitigation
- SO7. Structural change and generational renewal
- SO8. Jobs and growth in rural areas
- Vibrant rural areas
- Fostering knowledge and innovation

Project contribution to EU Strategies

- Achieving climate neutrality
- Improving management of natural resources used by agriculture, such as water, soil and air

EUR 7 013 862.50

Total budget

Total contributions including EU funding.

EUR 6 592 887.50

EU contribution

Any type of EU funding.

Project keyword(s)

Climate change (incl. GHG reduction, adaptation and mitigation, and other air related issues) >

Competitiveness/new business models > Digitalisation, incl. data and data technologies >

Rural issues > Social innovation >

Resources

Links

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[!\[\]\(e2376d476d06eb31946dc01a69a4403a_img.jpg\) YouTube channel !\[\]\(bbb3388d591ef640dd8a8c4262f2866a_img.jpg\)](#)

Audiovisual materials

[!\[\]\(d0a1791f26d167e866e44ebbf83efebe_img.jpg\) SMART ERA roll-up !\[\]\(cb1960474df5b19cdeae2009c7323e63_img.jpg\)](#)

[!\[\]\(5eb1325dfdc3f1cad8426726c0db51cd_img.jpg\) SMART ERA flyer !\[\]\(312638b5686dbc3f6ff8424fd17b3fb2_img.jpg\)](#)

[!\[\]\(eafc244b53721dd1ec133f0772f70fc7_img.jpg\) SMART ERA leaflet !\[\]\(cb741e910ae1fce3b15fcd4605753ff5_img.jpg\)](#)

[!\[\]\(d3fb9f94af8b26d1c844efa9a98805b0_img.jpg\) SMART ERA video presentation !\[\]\(78eb1652b591ce460bbb1a853a52e223_img.jpg\)](#)

8 Practice Abstracts

1. Improving access to health services for residents and tourists in nine villages in the Devetaki Plateau region, Bulgaria

The project addresses the issue of limited access to healthcare services in nine villages on the Devetaki Plateau.

Health services in this rural area are difficult to access due to poor organisation and a lack of public transport. This particularly affects the inhabitants of the nine villages, but also tourists. It impedes social inclusion, demographic growth and local economic development. In addition to limited access to healthcare, a lack of knowledge and expertise means that people travel to see their GP unnecessarily, putting extra pressure on doctors.

To address these issues, Sevlievo Municipality and the Devetaki Plateau Association (DPA) held co-creation workshops with stakeholders to develop a Smart Innovation Package (SIP). The SIP includes a user-friendly telemedicine tool for delivering health services remotely, enabling patients to consult doctors, receive diagnoses and monitor their health without visiting a hospital. This will improve access to medical care, particularly in remote areas, and enable a faster emergency response. The package also provides information and lectures on the most common diseases in rural areas, as well as advice on healthy living, food and the use of natural products.

Municipalities, NGOs and medical associations can adapt and use this model if they:

1. ensure the participation of all stakeholders
2. establish partnerships
3. plan activities in advance.
4. perform tests.

Benefits for end users:

- The elderly and families with children benefit from more accessible health services.
- Tourists get faster access to information and responses in the event of injury or accidents.
- General practitioners and specialists experience less pressure.
- The community has access to systematic, user-friendly information.

The main costs are related to coordination and setting up the digital infrastructure, but these can be minimised through partnerships and public funding.

[!\[\]\(d0262bbe9d2356661a2e89321dfcc781_img.jpg\) Devetaki Plateau, Central North Bulgaria website !\[\]\(8572950e410320d7dd023da827ff014d_img.jpg\)](#)

[!\[\]\(51514032c8ca341817228f39f1307b05_img.jpg\) News on local workshops to co-design a Smart Innovation Package !\[\]\(aba7c07a80262aa874bfebb3cd21d047_img.jpg\)](#)

[!\[\]\(c444627dab9fee9a1550c053ffaaaae2_img.jpg\) News on SIP CO-CREATION WORKSHOP IN KRAMOLIN !\[\]\(e4a71fb14267cbc3c68a54ad33289c8f_img.jpg\)](#)

Additional information

Geographical location: Nine villages in the area of the Devetaki Plateau, Central North Bulgaria

Facilitating elements:

- Community involvement in all stages of the project to build motivation and trust
- Partnership between the three municipalities in the region and the DPA
- Use of co-creation and facilitation tools

Barriers:

- Administrative burden in the existing health system and personal data management
- Conservatism of some users and the medical community towards innovation
- Different levels of knowledge and skills among users to apply and use technological solutions
- Limited long-term funding for the maintenance and upgrading of the technological service

Message to end users:

Although part of a national policy, access to health services can be brought closer to rural areas through innovation. Provided there is partnership and commitment from local authorities, the community, NGOs and professional stakeholders, smart solutions can be found and implemented in small villages. Participation and lifelong learning can help to improve quality of life, reverse negative demographic trends and promote local and economic development.

2. Enhancing the Dairy Supply Chain in Val di Sole: history, products, challenges, and opportunities

The dairy supply chain in Val di Sole is vital for the local economy, yet it is confronted with challenges such as generational turnover, limited market access, and the difficulty of demonstrating the value of its products. The SMART ERA project strengthens the connection between farmers, the local area, and the community by integrating the dairy sector with other vital local industries through a collective narrative supported by digital tools. This enhances the value of products and farmers' roles, thereby increasing competitiveness and sustainability. The project introduces innovative solutions that combine digitalisation, quality research, and direct sales. These include integrated traceability systems, mobile apps, blockchain technology for certifying data, producer dashboards and digital storytelling, which communicate the value of the work, boosting visibility and trust. Practices such as traceability, youth and school engagement, and cultural valorisation are planned in order to strengthen networking and collaboration across sectors. This replicable model blends tradition and innovation to improve profitability, sustainability and community cohesion. Local mayors, the Bruno Kessler Foundation and the Umse Territorial Cohesion Unit of the Autonomous Province of Trento are leading the process, which involves around twenty local stakeholders.

Recommendations: use digital tools to tell the story of farmers' work and communicate product value in order to increase visibility and trust; implement traceability in order to enhance transparency along the supply chain; engage with young people and schools in order to spread knowledge and enhance cultural

identity; strengthen networking between agriculture, tourism and education; support direct sales models in order to increase profitability and autonomy; and promote a replicable model that combines tradition and innovation.

Additional information

Geographical location: Italy - Trentino - Val di Sole

Various factors can support the implementation of the project results, including stimulating consumer interest in local and sustainable products, which drives demand for traceable goods. Integrating the project with tourism could help to de-seasonalise the offering and increase the area's appeal. Furthermore, digitalisation can reduce management costs and increase product visibility.

However, there are also some obstacles. Resistance to change among some farmers, particularly those who are less familiar with technology, could hinder the adoption process. The initial costs of training and implementing traceability systems may be difficult to bear without adequate support. Furthermore, establishing a traceability system necessitates robust infrastructure and coordination among various stakeholders, which can be challenging to achieve.

To overcome these barriers, it is recommended that training is strengthened and technical support is provided for farmers. Local institutions could also offer financial incentives to help cover initial investments. Furthermore, ongoing research into best practices would allow for the continuous improvement of implemented models, making them more responsive to sector-specific needs.

Looking ahead, it will be essential to monitor market developments and collect feedback from practitioners in order to adapt the project to real-world needs and thus ensure the long-term sustainability and competitiveness of the dairy supply chain.

3. Breaking data silos in rural tourism destination

Surrounded by the Tramuntana mountain range and the Mediterranean Sea, the Valley of Sóller is a rural territory that relies heavily on tourism, but also on agriculture (especially with the production of citrics and olives), as main economic drivers. The high seasonality of these sectors, combined with a high degree of tourism massification and a decline of the traditional agricultural sector, are generating important socioeconomic issues. This is exacerbated by a brain drain phenomenon, causing negative demographic growth, and by poor digitalisation and lack of data sharing in the region: connectivity is still a major issue; low offer of digital services by municipality and local companies; lack of knowledge and competences in technology and innovation of local stakeholders; limited availability of data, and extremely low level of data-sharing and integration between local stakeholders.

The project aims to address these challenges through digitalisation of the local industrial ecosystem, and through the implementation of digital services and activities that contribute to improving the sustainable development of the town while retaining the local population and enhancing the coexistence between residents and tourists. In particular, the project aims to foster data sharing between the tourism and

agricultural sectors, enabling the monitoring of key indicators, the identification of new products, services and business models that could contribute to diversification of the local economy and a better distribution all year-round. As such, a data platform will be implemented for stakeholders to share their data, and specific training programmes will be implemented to upskill local workforce and raise knowledge and awareness on digitalization, innovation, and sustainability, among others. This will contribute to increasing the digital literacy of the population, and to ensuring the success and uptake of the digital services to be provided within the municipality.

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[!\[\]\(d219eb33a83c47f5c6c63c27bbe267cb_img.jpg\) SIP Workshop Video by AnySolution !\[\]\(b3b0a188e99a57a4c6164a3c675ba63f_img.jpg\)](#)

Additional information

Geographical location: Valley of Sóller, Mallorca, Balearic Islands, Spain

One of the main challenges to carrying out the project concerns the unshared and uncoordinated vision among the different sectors and stakeholders. There is no, or very little cooperation among them. However, the implementation of codesign and cocreation workshops, using the SMART ERA' Smart Innovation Package toolkit (SIP toolkit), greatly helped to gather stakeholders and discuss the solutions and actions to be implemented. Indeed, the involvement and engagement of the local community is key for the success of such initiatives.

Another fundamental aspect is the need to raise awareness and knowledge. Most stakeholders do not share their data as they are unaware of its potential, benefits, and/or value, or simply because they don't know how to do it.

Tourism massification (overtourism) is becoming a significant issue. Implementation of digital tools enabling a better monitoring and distribution of tourism flow within the territory is a must. Integration of alternative tourism experiences based on rural tourism, local products, and natural, cultural and historical heritage, can contribute to improving the diversification of the tourism offerings, and alleviate massification at "hot spots".

4. Limited public transport in rural areas affects access and inclusion. A community-developed on-demand mobility service connects key services, fosters...

The project addresses the need for flexible, inclusive and sustainable transport in rural communities with ageing populations and poor connectivity. In places such as Šmarje and Padna, elderly residents, young people, and non-drivers struggle to access services, while local producers lack visibility and face logistical challenges. Traditional transport options are limited, and digital exclusion exacerbates these issues.

Through co-creation workshops, the community has designed an on-demand mobility service that is coordinated by a local NGO and supported by municipalities, the university, and citizens. This solution combines a user-friendly mobile app with local operators and volunteers, providing links to essential

services such as schools, health centres, farms, and tourist attractions. It also incorporates elements of the circular economy, such as connections to agri-tourism and local food delivery services. Community trust is built through shared ownership, local engagement, and transparency.

Practical implications:

Rural practitioners, municipalities and SMEs can replicate this model using a simple process.

Identify key user needs (e.g. elderly people or producers).

Involve users via participatory design.

Build a local partnership network.

Use open-source or low-cost digital tools.

Start small and scale up gradually.

Benefits:

- Greater mobility and independence for the elderly and young people.

- Better visibility and sales channels for farmers.

- Local job creation and digital inclusion

Strengthened community bonds

Costs and coordination:

The initial setup includes coordination (approx. €10,000 per year) and the development of a digital tool (€5,000–€15,000). These costs can be reduced through voluntary contributions and funding from public sources (e.g. rural development and social innovation). The target population is up to 500 residents, with 30 plus regular users expected in the first phase.

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[!\[\]\(758fecfcf97b15b743a123b5de83ec46_img.jpg\) LinkedIN page of Središče Rotunda !\[\]\(63862fd6a45c776b9dc26f1b0288aca7_img.jpg\)](#)

[!\[\]\(19fdbd6eaa1508fb9caf367b7a64e245_img.jpg\) Središče Rotunda official webpage with the informations regarding SMART ERA pro... !\[\]\(20bf40fca7b7cd295d75375262bf46fa_img.jpg\)](#)

[!\[\]\(007bb571fc5331b364ae27ddf8a1c148_img.jpg\) Šmarje \(Municipality of Koper\) !\[\]\(1d3aecdb206eba3eb47893067d67ca67_img.jpg\)](#)

[!\[\]\(bfa23e0309ec40163031a78578652da3_img.jpg\) Padna \(Municipality of Piran\) !\[\]\(de9fdd756ecc1b3ec0eac51d419a893c_img.jpg\)](#)

Additional information

Geographical Location: Šmarje (Municipality of Koper) and Padna (Municipality of Piran) / Slovenian Istria
– rural region in the Littoral area of Slovenia.

Recommendations for future actions:

- Develop dedicated support instruments for digital mobility pilots in rural areas.

- Train local digital mentors to assist users of mobility services and apps.

- Establish a national framework that integrates rural mobility, digital inclusion and the circular economy.

Facilitating elements:

- Strong community engagement and trust
- Synergy with existing Smart Village initiatives (e.g. local hubs for tourism and food innovation).
- Support from local NGOs and academic institutions.

Obstacles:

- Complex administrative procedures for grassroots initiatives.
- Lack of stable, long-term funding for service continuity.
- Varying levels of digital literacy among rural residents

Message to end users:

Even the smallest villages can become drivers of smart rural innovation. With your participation, local ideas can be turned into real solutions that connect people, improve quality of life and sustain vibrant rural communities. Start local — think smart!

5. A new method of smartness assessment for rural areas: SESAM; the Smart ERA Smartness Assessment Method

Poliedra, in cooperation with all project partners, has tried to meet the need of having a standardised way to assess the level of smartness, defined as the level of digital maturity or readiness, of rural and mountain areas. A standardised norm exists does exist to assess the smartness of cities and communities (namely ISO standard 37122:2019), but no such norm exists for rural areas. SESAM's development started from a literature review of smartness assessment methods, both qualitative and quantitative, and from the careful evaluation of ISO standard 37122:2019. As a general structure, SESAM has both a qualitative and a quantitative path, aiming to clarify the needs and expectations of rural areas in terms of digital transition, and quantifying them. The project's rural areas have tested SESAM at different levels, and have found it user friendly and flexible enough for their scope: those who wanted a general overview could make use of only the qualitative path, whereas those who wanted a more thorough assessment could delve more deeply in the evaluation of a selected smartness indicators. SESAM's quantitative path is composed of six dimensions of smartness: from Enabling Factors to Economy, from Governance & Policies to Mobility & Transport, from Environment & Climate to Services to the populations. SESAM's qualitative path includes a survey on the relevance , for each rural area, of the dimensions listed above, as well as the possibility of emotional mapping, which gauges the emotional response of local populations to various aspects and features of their own area. SESAM has been designed to allow rural and mountain areas to assess, qualitatively and/or quantitatively, their own level of digital maturity and/or readiness, which help them in setting priorities for their own community-led digital transitions.

[!\[\]\(eaac180de418db4eae4b4cefebda75e8_img.jpg\) Deliverable 2.1 "Smartness Assessment methodology" !\[\]\(bfaddf7f6c96014da25ff5a29789658b_img.jpg\)](#)

Additional information

Geographical location: All rural areas included in SMART ERA - the ambition is to set a smartness assessment standard.

27 different smartness assessment methodologies were assessed and evaluated in the literature review, a key aspect in the creation of SESAM. Moreover, the evaluation and assessment of ISO standard 37122:2019 was also important, as it helped understand how a smartness assessment standard was created and works. The partnership thought that SESAM could become an expansion of ISO standard 37122:2019, and if not, a new international standard to gauge and assess the level of digital maturity and readiness of rural and mountain areas. To this end, Poliedra with Fondazione Bruno Kessler and ICONS have already contacted the Italian entity for standardisation (UNI) and will start an exploratory process aimed at understanding whether SESAM could indeed form the basis for a new expanded ISO standard, or even a new ISO standard. As of April 2025, the process toward this has begun.

The possible obstacles are mostly connected to the possible complexity of SESAM for groups of local stakeholders, and the possible need for guidance and facilitation while compiling the quantitative path in particular: this is also the main reason why SESAM also includes a possible more ready to use qualitative path.

6. Revitalising Local Rural Communities through Digital Platforms: Piloting Platform Economy Solutions

Northern Ostrobothnia is a largely rural region of Finland facing demographic and structural challenges. Many areas are experiencing population decline and limited access to services, which is putting pressure on local businesses. The ageing population and the centralisation of services have made it more difficult for residents, particularly the elderly and those without private transport, to access everyday services. At the same time, rural entrepreneurs often struggle to reach new customers and traditional channels may no longer suffice. However, digitalisation and the rise of remote working present new opportunities to invigorate local economies and communities.

Against this backdrop, a centrally operated digital service platform is being developed and tested in the municipalities of Alavieska, Kalajoki, and Nivala. The platform connects local service providers from various sectors, such as tourism operators, cultural organisations, and care services, more efficiently with residents, remote workers, and visitors. Rather than offering services itself, the platform functions as a digital meeting point where supply and demand can more easily match. Inspired by services such as Airbnb and Uber, this model is tailored to local needs and is available for use by small-scale entrepreneurs and communities.

Workshops with residents and service providers have revealed strong interest in easier access to local services and better visibility for providers. The platform's key characteristics include ease of use, safety, access to up-to-date information, and a diverse range of services. Providers benefit from increased reach and visibility at a low cost, while users gain convenient access to relevant services. Social cohesion and local networks are recognised as strengths to build upon.

Development will continue in 2025, with pilot implementation planned for 2026. The model is scaleable and can support rural economies, entrepreneurship and quality of life in other regions.

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[Municipality of Alavieska website](#)

[City of Kalajoki website](#)

[City of Nivala website](#)

Additional information

Geographical location: Northern Ostrobothnia, Finland - Municipality of Alavieska - City of Kalajoki - City of Nivala.

Facilitating elements: High local interest, strong sense of community, and willingness of municipalities to support coordination and onboarding.

Obstacles: Initial awareness-raising is needed.

Future actions: Continued co-development with users; piloting the platform in real-world conditions in 2026.

Messages to end-users:

- Local service providers: Listing your services on the platform can expand your customer base with minimal effort or cost.
- Residents and remote workers: Use the platform to easily discover services in your area and support local businesses.
- Municipalities and community organisations: Consider adopting and tailoring the model to support rural development and service access in your area.

7. East Herzegovina - from a region affected by depopulation to a rural tourism destination

Situation: East Herzegovina is a south-eastern micro-region of Bosnia and Herzegovina centred on the city of Trebinje, comprising seven smaller municipalities. Geographically and climatically, the region can be divided into two areas: Lower Herzegovina, with an altitude of less than 500m and a Mediterranean climate; and Upper Herzegovina, with an altitude of more than 500m and a mountain climate. The region's biodiversity is very rich, with numerous endemic species. East Herzegovina is an unspoilt region boasting outstanding landscapes, a rich cultural and historical heritage, and unique gastronomy. However, it is the least populated region in the country, with only 15.26 inhabitants per km² (Institute of Statistics of the Republic of Srpska, 2017). This trend has worsened to the point where it could be called an exodus. Highly educated people, as well as the younger reproductive population, are leaving the region. This disrupts the age structure and leads to depopulation.

Solution: The application of SIPs (Smart Innovative Packages) will raise the profile of East Herzegovina as a rural tourism destination on the global map. A digital platform will be developed containing an interactive map showing cultural and historical sites, households offering tourist services, tourist information and

guides. It will also provide information on local events and activities as well as customisable itineraries. It will be the first local platform to process the tourist offerings of regional rural areas.

The platform will increase:

- 1) the region's visibility,
- 2) the number of visitors,
- 3) the income of small-scale producers of local products.

The cultural, natural and gastronomic heritage will be digitalised by involving the most knowledgeable and vulnerable groups: young people and rural women.

[🔗 Slow Food Trebinje Herzegovina website](#)

[🔗 Slow Food Trebinje Herzegovina Facebook page](#)

[🔗 Tourist Board of Republic of Srpska website](#)

[🔗 Slow Food International Ark of Taste product from Bosnia and Herzegovina](#)

[🔗 Article: Cheese in a sac: exploring history, production area and production pro...](#)

[🔗 Tourist Board of Trebinje website](#)

[🔗 Tourist Board of Bileća Facebook page](#)

[🔗 Tourist Board of Gacko Facebook page](#)

[🔗 Tourist Board of Nevesinje website](#)

[🔗 Tourist Board of Kalinovik website](#)

[🔗 The most beautiful village Bratač Facebook page](#)

[🔗 Book: Nutritional and Health Aspects of Food in the Balkans](#)

Additional information

Geographical location: East Herzegovina with one city, Trebinje, and seven municipalities: Berkovici, Bileca, Gacko, Istocni Mostar, Kalinovik, Ljubinje and Nevesinje

After the Covid pandemic, the world as we knew it disappeared, and all sectors of the economy experienced completely new trends, which is particularly evident in tourism. In addition to viruses brought

about by climate change, global warming has also made villages more desirable places to live in than big cities. Rural tourism is the fastest-growing branch of tourism.

The digital solution for Eastern Herzegovina will have two components: the first will allow small-scale producers and other regional stakeholders to enter and update their data, while the second will be oriented towards tourists.

The following obstacles may be encountered when using the platform:

- a) Problems entering and updating data due to the low level of computer literacy among small-scale producers
- b) Financial issues regarding platform maintenance

Future research should focus on diversifying activities on rural farms to make them as resilient as possible.

8. SMART ERA Co-Design Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement in Rural Innovation Development

Designing and implementing socio-technical innovations to tackle rural development issues is a complex and multifaceted process. The EU-funded SMART ERA project addresses this challenge by empowering local communities to actively engage in creating innovative solutions tailored to their unique needs. A co-design toolkit has been developed to involve local stakeholders in creating Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs)—customised solutions combining both technological and non-technological components to address rural challenges. To support this process, the toolkit identifies key 'ingredients'—social, economic, technological, political, and infrastructural elements—essential for designing effective interventions. The co-design toolkit includes both analog and digital components.

The analog toolkit includes ingredient information cards, reflection prompts, support canvases, and a visual progress tracking board. These resources encourage critical reflection on rural communities' needs, available resources, and transformative capacities.

The digital component complements the analog tool by providing real-time monitoring, asynchronous collaboration, and gamified engagement. It integrates a digital version of the tracking board, visual feedback, and recognition mechanisms, allowing communities to co-create SIPs in a flexible environment.

By combining digital efficiency with analog strengths, the toolkit enhances accessibility, participatory governance, and community resilience, contributing to sustainable rural development and autonomous rural initiatives.

Practical implications: The co-design toolkit is offered to organisations who steer the community engagement processes to help them guide sessions with rural communities and help them assess their needs, resources, and desired solutions through co-design workshops, inter-sectoral dialogue, and creative envisioning. Currently supported languages are Bulgarian, English, Finnish, Italian, Serbian, Slovenian and Spanish.

Additional information

Geographical Location:

The toolkit was developed and is currently being evaluated in six pilot areas located in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Finland, Italy, Slovenia, and Spain.

Complementarity with other methods:

- The toolkit complements established, general-purpose, co-design and community-led approaches by providing tailored materials that focus on the key dimensions of rural innovation.
- Rather than aiming to be exhaustive, the toolkit provides a structured methodology for categorising and illustrating potential ingredients. Users are encouraged to build upon it with their own ideas, insights, and local knowledge.

Obstacles:

- Innovation is a long-term, incremental process—often unfolding through iterative cycles.
- No single co-design pathway can suit every territory or rural challenge.

Overcoming obstacles and accommodating different contexts:

- The toolkit avoids prescribing a one-size-fits-all model. Instead, it offers both inspiration and practical guidance to help rural communities assemble suites of technological and non-technological "ingredients" that are adapted to their unique contexts.
- Designed for flexibility and adaptability, the toolkit supports diverse design journeys and development paces. It can be used across a range of settings, from formal institutional frameworks to informal grassroots initiatives.

Open development for future extensions:

- The toolkit is conceived as a living resource that can evolve over time by incorporating feedback and new materials aligned with the goals and structure of the innovation process. Its value lies not only in the content it provides, but also in its adaptability and potential to be shaped and integrated with familiar local approaches and methodologies. Community ownership and creative adaptation are therefore essential to fully unlock its potential.

Contacts

Project email

✉ info@smartera-project.eu

Project coordinator

Fondazione Bruno Kessler

Project coordinator

✉ pmg@fbk.eu 🌐 [Website](#) 📞 +39 0461 314561 📍 Via Sommarive 18 ☰ Research institute

Project partners

UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI

Project partner

☰ Researcher or research organisation

OULUN YLIOPISTO

Project partner

☰ Researcher or research organisation

SOFTWARE COMPETENCE CENTER HAGENBERG GMBH

Project partner

☰ Other

**POLIEDRA-CENTRO DI SERVIZIO E CONSULENZA DEL
POLITECNICO DI MILANO SUPIANIFICAZIONE
AMBIENTALE E TERRITORIALE CONSORZIO**

Project partner

UNIVERZA V MARIBORU

Project partner

☰ Researcher or research organisation

ENGINEERING - INGEGNERIA INFORMATICA SPA

Project partner

☰ Industry

FONDAZIONE ICONS

Project partner

☰ NGO

**ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE POUR L'INNOVATION DANS
LE DEVELOPPEMENT LOCAL**

Project partner

☰ NGO

ANYSOLUTION SL

Project partner

☰ SME

SLOW FOOD TREBINJE HERCEGOVINA

Project partner

☰ NGO

DEVETASHKO PLATO SDRUZHENIE

Project partner

☰ NGO

PROVINCIA AUTONOMA DI TRENTO

Project partner

☰ Public Authority

SREDISCE ROTUNDA, PRIMORSKI DRUZHENI CENTER, KOPER, SO.P. SREDISCE ROTUNDA, CENTRO SOCIALE DEL LITORALE, CAPODISTRIA, SO.P

Project partner

☰ NGO

POHJOIS-POHJANMAAN LIITTO

Project partner

☰ Public Authority

MES CULTURA TURISME I PATRIMONI SL

Project partner

☰ NGO

TURISTICKA ORGANIZACIJA REPUBLIKE SRPSKE

Project partner

☰ Public Authority

SUOMEN ITAMERI-INSTITUUTIN SAATIO SR

Project partner

☰ Researcher or research organisation

FUNDINGBOX ACCELERATOR SP ZOO

Project partner

☰ Industry

SCHWEIZERISCHEN ARBEITSGEMEINSCHAFT FUER DIE BERGGEBIETE (SAB)

Project partner

☰ Researcher or research organisation

Sluzba Vlade Republike Slovenije za razvoj in evropsko kohezijsko politiko

Project partner

☰ Public Authority

STADT WIEN

Project partner

☰ Advisor, advisory organisation or agricultural chamber

OBSHTINA SEVLIEVO

Project partner

☰ Public Authority

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